

ABOUT SOME METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES IN NON- LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the main methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language, which influence the development of communicative competence of foreign students, and new methods for teaching Russian in non-linguistic universities.

The methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, like any independent discipline, also has its own conceptual apparatus. The basic concepts that form the foundation of the methodology include: process, goals, content, principles, methods, techniques, means and organizational forms of training. Taken together, they constitute a system of methodological categories that make it possible to adequately describe options for teaching Russian as a foreign language in different conditions. The listed components are systemic formations and are aimed at achieving a single goal - language teaching. They are closely related to each other and are manifested in each specific act of educational activity. They are formed under the influence of the environment, which dictates the requirements of what and how to teach in connection with the needs of society and are united with each other through training. All components of the training system are in a certain hierarchical relationship with each other. But the dominant role in the system belongs to learning goals, which are formed under the influence of the environment and influence the choice of approach to learning, methods, principles, means and organizational forms of learning. Through the listed components, the training system is implemented in the form of an educational process, the organizational and structural unit of which is in speech practice classes. In the educational process, such a component as the learning goal turns out to be very important. Goals are understood as the expected results of the joint activities of the teacher and students. Goals influence the choice of content, principles, forms, methods and means of teaching.

The practical (communicative) goal is to develop foreign students' communicative competence and ability to communicate in Russian. The universal means of communication is language. Other sign systems (gestures, facial expressions, signals, pointers) are used only in specific conditions and convey information limited by these conditions, therefore, when they talk about learning to communicate, they mean teaching speech activity. The communicative goal in this case is the formation and development of speech skills, the ability to communicate using linguistic means. In the context of Russian as a foreign language, much attention is paid to the formation of non-verbal communication skills, or the ability to use non-verbal means of communication (gestures, facial expressions).

The unit of modeling in the process of teaching the Russian language is a communicative situation, which should be understood as a dynamic system of interacting specific factors of an objective and subjective nature (including speech), involving a person in linguistic communication and determining his behavior within one act of communication. The communicative situation is made up of four factors:

- 1) the circumstances of reality (the setting) in which communication takes place;
- 2) relationships between communicating (communicants);
- 3) speech motivation (that is, what contributed to the beginning of communication);
- 4) the implementation of the act of communication itself, during which a new position is created, new stimuli for speech appear, in other words, the continuation of verbal communication is ensured [1].

It is well known that the direct method is a method of teaching oral speech that models the conditions of the natural method of mastering a foreign language (i.e., the method of mastering a foreign language in the process of communicating with its native speakers). This method is similar to how a child masters his native language. A foreign language is acquired by imitation of ready-made models, repeated repetition of what has been heard and reproduction of new material by analogy with what has been learned. In modern methodological literature, the curricula of the course "Russian as a foreign language" or "Russian language by specialty", as a rule, are focused on various levels of general proficiency in the Russian language (elementary, basic, etc.) depending on specific conditions and communicative needs students.

Teaching Russian as a foreign language has recently been usually considered as teaching intercultural communication, since it represents communication between a representative of Russian culture - a teacher of the Russian language and foreign students,

which is carried out in the process of educational and pedagogical cooperation between teacher and student [2]. Teachers, trying to diversify the educational process and maximize its effectiveness, carry out a great deal of creative work in choosing the most suitable textbooks; from those already available, first of all, of course, a huge variety of exercises (written and oral) are created. For more targeted work, it is important to take into account that during the learning process, foreign students gain knowledge of systemic relations in the Russian language, along with the acquisition of communicative skills (phonetics, grammar, reading, listening, writing) converge at one point - the use of acquired knowledge in communication. As for phonetics, the teaching of this section cannot be purely aspect-based, since when studying phonetics, one enters into speech practice. The ultimate goal of speech activity is the ability to understand Russian speech and conduct a conversation with native speakers of the target language [3].

The primary question arises of how to correctly and timely organize communication activities in various communication situations. The principle of work is to teach by aspect, that is, in a grammar lesson, students gain new knowledge on a certain section of grammar, then perform exercises according to the model, read texts permeated with this grammar; During a speech practice class, they compose new dialogues based on models, learn dialogues from the textbook by heart, perform oral exercises within the framework of the textbook and workbook, listen to lesson CDs, and complete listening tasks. This technique, in our opinion, is very effective. I would especially like to note a reading guide for foreigners starting to learn the Russian language called "The Box" by O.E. Chubarova. This manual includes about one hundred small texts with post-text assignments. The texts are adapted and correspond to the program for the elementary level of general proficiency in the Russian language. The structure of the manual is as follows: introduction to the six cases takes place within the framework of relevant entertaining texts; new vocabulary is highlighted in bold and translated into English, which is also very convenient for the student, since foreign students speak English to one degree or another.

It is well known that role-playing games stimulate the development of students' spontaneous speech and help overcome language and psychological barriers. Modern education is aimed at preparing students not only to adapt, but also to actively master situations of social change. In the Russian language lesson, a special place is occupied by forms of classes that ensure the active participation of each student in the lesson, stimulate verbal communication, and contribute to the formation of interest and desire to learn a foreign language, in particular the Russian language. These problems can be solved using game teaching methods. In the game, the abilities of any person, and especially the abilities of students at the initial stage of education, can be fully demonstrated. A game is a specially organized activity that requires intense emotional and mental strength. The game involves making a decision - what to do, what to say? The desire to solve these issues sharpens the mental activity of the players. And if students speak Russian, the game opens up rich learning opportunities. Being entertainment and relaxation, a game can develop into learning, creativity, and a model of human relationships [4]. This can include, for example, the dialogue "In the store"; dialogical speech between the buyer and the seller can take place in the following stores: "Clothing", "Shoes", "Electrical goods", "Cookware", "Stationery", the corresponding information must first be given vocabulary and models (samples), where the

same student can act as both a buyer and a seller. Games such as "Insert the letter", "Competition game", "Crossword game", "Description of appearance and character", "Where is the object?" and many other games will be equally useful when working in pairs or independently. We would also like to include the presentation of song texts that reflect the current state of the language of the society speaking it as non-traditional methods. The text we took to solve any methodological problem can well be used as an educational one.

In modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, various approaches are being developed that would optimize the volume of material being studied and speed up the course of its assimilation. The most optimal and effective nowadays are printed and audio media. Song material from the country of the language being studied, combining the characteristic features of printed text and audio material, is an interesting and useful additional material when studying a foreign language (in this case, Russian as a foreign language) and getting to know the country, its customs, literary and musical creativity.

One of the most effective ways to influence the feelings and emotions of students is music, which is a powerful mental stimulant that penetrates into the hidden depths of consciousness. The apex at which all acquired language knowledge, skills and abilities are summed up, and the main unit of learning is the text. When selecting texts in the study of the Russian language in non-linguistic universities, it should be taken into account that a person, according to psychological data, remembers much more deeply and quickly what is close to him, what he experiences emotionally [1]. Therefore, the song, combining the characteristic features of printed text and audio material, is a universal tool for teaching Russian as a foreign language; it should also be noted that students perceive this presentation of the material with great interest, both in listening and grammar. Watching films is also of keen interest, both in class and outside: in a cinema with a teacher or watching films on your own at home. Of course, this situation is relevant at advanced stages of training. One should also take into account the fact that when watching a film, much remains incomprehensible to the student; in order to avoid this problem, it is necessary to work in detail with the text; it is useful to hold round tables and seminars. Work on the film is based on a detailed analysis of the film text and subsequent viewing in order to develop skills in listening to the spontaneous speech of native speakers. The text material is divided into episodes, the teacher highlights difficult moments that require comment. And today, students' interest in historical films continues; they not only watch them, but also create their own individual projects based on what they saw. At the initial stage of training, foreign students are able to understand cartoons with minimal use of vocabulary; this type of work can be carried out after writing a test, a control paper, thereby filling the remaining time from the lesson. The following animated films may be offered for viewing: "Well, wait a minute!", "The Lion Cub and the Turtle", "The Tale of the Fisherman and the Fish" and many others. The excursion method also helps to enrich the vocabulary through special and everyday vocabulary. "Portfolio" is a multifaceted and very fashionable trend in modern life; in our work, "portfolio" is used in the form of a "language portfolio," which is a collection of materials that demonstrate the results of educational activities in mastering the Russian language. Modern higher school needs teaching methods that would help not only to provide high-quality training, but, first of all, to develop the potential of the individual.

The above methods will help expand the knowledge of young teachers, help them develop communicative competence and facilitate the process of adaptation of foreign students to the Russian language environment. As a result, it should be assumed that the main goal of the subject "Russian as a foreign language" or "Russian language" in non-linguistic universities is the formation of communicative competence, that is, the ability and willingness of students to carry out foreign language interpersonal communication with native speakers with access to a dialogue of cultures. Dialogue of cultures involves: introducing students to the culture of the country of the language being studied, which helps them better understand their own culture. So, taking into account the relevance of teaching students of non-linguistic universities in universities of Uzbekistan, as well as the conditions of fierce competition in the global market of educational services and the need to improve the quality of education, we can conclude that for the successful process of developing students' communicative competence it is necessary to develop and implement new methods in the educational process and forms of teaching.

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